

METAL STRUCTURES AND THEIR ROLE IN MODERN ARCHITECTURE.

Ubaydullaev Abdilbase Suvankulovich

senior lecturer of the department of “Construction of Buildings and Structures” Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute
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Annotation: This article discusses the development of the construction industry, metal structures in modern times, the use of metal structures in the construction industry, the increasing popularity of their use at the present time, the advantages and disadvantages of metal structures, the design of metal structures in the construction industry, the use of metal structures from an architectural point of view, the ability of metal structures to perceive large loads with relative lightness, the requirements imposed on metal structures when they are used.

Keywords: Construction industry, reliability, industriality, impermeability, corrosion, aesthetics

The development of technologies in the construction industry, and the increase in the pace of construction of residential and non-residential buildings, has led to an increase in the demand for metal structures in the construction industry. The increase in popularity of metal structures in recent years is due not only to their high performance, but also to their widespread use in construction. Metal structures are used in the construction of modern shopping malls, high-tech industrial and industrial buildings, sports facilities, and warehouses.

In modern times, metal structures are the optimal solution when it is necessary to create a reliable structure of a large area. Due to the possibility of manufacturing various metal structures, the time and laboriousness of the construction of buildings and structures is significantly reduced.

From an architectural point of view, metal structures are not only beams, trusses, ties, girders, columns and arches, but also enclosing and secondary structures, architectural elements of frames and components of prefabricated buildings.

The use of metal structures allows to achieve the maximum effect in the external appearance of buildings and structures, and in some cases, it becomes an incentive to create new images and the birth of exclusive architectural ideas.

Metal structures have the following advantages, allowing them to be used in a variety of structures.

The ability to perceive large loads with relative lightness and small dimensions of structures, due to the high strength of steel; despite the small specific gravity of steel (7.85 t/m³), structures made of steel have a lower weight compared to structures made of other building materials; due to the high strength of the material, steel structures are small-sized, which makes them convenient for transportation; [3].

The reliability of metal structures is ensured by the close coincidence of their actual work (stress and strain distribution) with the calculated assumptions. The material of metal structures (steel, aluminum alloys) has a high uniformity of structure and closely corresponds to the calculated assumptions about the elastic or elastic-plastic work of the material.[1]

Industriality. Most metal structures are manufactured at factories equipped with modern equipment, which ensures a high degree of industrial manufacturing. The installation of metal structures is also very industrial, as it is carried out by specialized organizations using high-performance equipment.

Impenetrability. Metals have not only considerable strength, but also high density - impermeability to gases and liquids. The density of the metal and its joints, carried out by welding, is a necessary condition for the manufacture and erection of sheet structures.[2].

Metal structures are easily repaired. Strengthening, reconstruction and technical re-equipment of steel structures is quite simple. Using welding, it is possible to weld new technological elements to the existing frame, if it is necessary to increase the rigidity of the structural elements and, moreover, it is very easy and simple from the technological point of view.

And also metal structures have a number of disadvantages that limit their use in need of measures to neutralize these disadvantages.

Corrosion. Not protected from the action of a humid atmosphere, and sometimes (even worse) contaminated with aggressive gases, steel corrodes (oxidizes), which gradually leads to its complete destruction. Under unfavorable conditions, this can happen in two to three years. Although aluminum alloys are significantly more resistant to corrosion, they also corrode under adverse conditions. Cast iron resists corrosion well.

An increase in the corrosion resistance of metal structures is achieved by including special alloying elements in steel, periodically coating the structures with protective films (varnishes, paints, etc.), as well as choosing a rational structural shape of the elements (without slots and sinuses where moisture and dust can accumulate), convenient for cleaning and protection.[2]

Fire resistance at objects unsafe in terms of fire safety (warehouses with combustible or flammable materials, buildings and structures) is increased by avoiding direct contact of metal structures with an open flame. To do this, the design provides for fire-resistant cladding, suspended ceilings, coatings with special compounds. The fire resistance limit of metal structures when using special coatings in the form of coatings is significantly increased.

When designing metal structures, the following requirements should be taken into account:

Operating conditions. Satisfaction with the operating conditions specified during the design is the main requirement for the designer. It basically determines the system, the structural form of the structure and the choice of material for it.

Metal savings. The requirement to save metal is determined by its great need in all industries (engineering, transport, etc.) and its relatively high cost.

Transportability. In connection with the manufacture of metal structures, as a rule, in factories with subsequent transportation to the construction site, the project should provide for the possibility of transporting them in whole or in parts (mandrel elements) using appropriate vehicles.

Aesthetics. Designs, regardless of their purpose, must have harmonious forms. This requirement is especially important for public buildings and structures.[2]

The role of metal structures will especially increase when construction is shifted to remote areas that require widespread use of light metal structures. A further direction in the industrialization of the construction of industrial, transport, energy, and other facilities will be widely used light metal structures.

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